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Transitioning Experience: Migrant Learning and Engaging with Canada's Labour Market Challenges

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Abstract

Context: Newcomers to Canada are commonly expected to possess localized experience to gain full labour market access. It represents a canon of tacit knowledge to be acquired, for instance through volunteer work or employment below individuals' level of qualification. Whereas the exclusionary effects of the Canadian Experience (CE) discourse have been well-documented, less is known about how individuals learn to engage with CE. This paper thus aims to elucidate and conceptualize this aspect of learning during transitions into new work contexts and to draw conclusions for practice.

Approach: Taking a *doing transitions* and *doing migration* perspective, 20 biographical-narrative interviews were conducted in 2021 with persons who had moved to Canada as adults. The data were analysed using the documentary method which focuses not only on the thematic (what) but primarily on the implicit (how) dimensions of the narrations.

Findings: Three modes of engaging with CE: *Replay and readjust* is marked by repeated setbacks, frustrations, and – seemingly – resignation. *Reset and move forward* is marked by a lowering of aspirations and an alignment of future life course decisions with the need to acquire CE. *Research and pro-act* is characterized by excelling at knowing the rules and playing the game.

Conclusion: The analysis of the engagement with migratory challenges points to aids in conceptualizing learning in transitions and its social embeddedness. For the practice of supporting worklife transitions in the context of migration, the findings suggest differentiated provision not only of factual knowledge about labour markets but of guidance and spaces for processing experiences.

Keywords: transitions, migration, adult learning, qualitative methods

1 Introduction

Transitions to and through working life can be associated with a range of changes, including changes in employment status, change in occupation, change in lifestyle or change in location (Billett et al., 2021). In the case of adults migrating – broadly understood as changing residence across administrative borders (Haas et al., 2020, p. 23) – these changes may coincide, requiring individuals to learn, to adapt, and to deal with unexpected challenges as will be the focus of this paper.

During migratory transitions, individuals' previously acquired skills, experience, and qualifications become salient in two ways: First, through processes of formal reassessment, validation or devaluation of credentials (Guo & Shan, 2013; Kloubert & Hoggan, 2021; Nohl et al., 2014). Second and less formally, through the need to transfer and translate the non-

credentialized experience and skills into new labour market and workplace contexts. Whereas bringing experience from diverse geographical, occupational and cultural backgrounds into new contexts can beget creativity and innovation (Shan, 2023), this process of entering the new labour market is fraught with potential challenges. These include restricted access to the labour market and employability-oriented training (Bağcı, 2019; Ellis & Triantaphyllidu, 2023; Liu & Guo, 2021), precarious employment (Hande et al., 2020) and employment below their level of qualification, also referred to as a „brain waste” or a „discounting of skills” (Reitz et al., 2014). Of particular interest in this paper is the – somewhat paradoxical – requirement to possess localized work experience in order to gain access to the local labour market. In the context of the Canadian immigration and labour market regime, this is discussed as *Canadian Experience* (CE).

CE can first be understood as a body of implicit knowledge that is localized, hard to articulate and yet often must be acquired by immigrants to find employment commensurate with their qualifications (Sakamoto et al., 2010). Exploring the contradictions between the stated need for skilled immigrants in Canada and their well-documented labour market challenges, Sakamoto et al. observed a broad array of conceptual understandings of CE with its hard dimensions (technical capabilities) and soft dimensions (communication skills). As a result, the authors propose the use of the concept *tacit knowledge*, which „affords us a more sophisticated understanding of Canadian experience, this elusive yet persistent requirement that skilled immigrants face before accessing successful employment” (Sakamoto et al., 2010, p. 150). Second, the discourse on CE can be conceptualized as a „rhetorical tool” for nation building through branding, understood as a „process of affective identification with an imagined national identity” (Bhuyan et al., 2017, 49, 51). In this sense, CE acts as a „brand” that serves to „re-envision Canada’s White policy within a neoliberal context by relying on the capacity of immigrant others to embody traits of Whiteness in a neoliberal era: self-sufficiency, autonomy, flexibility and utility in the market place” (Bhuyan et al., 2017, p. 60). Third, as argued by Ku et al. (2018), CE can act as a smokescreen for racist practices and enable „racism without racists” by steering the public to...

viewing immigrant difficulties as individual deficits, explainable by their ‘foreign’ credentials, their lack of preparedness, their low status in Canadian social hierarchy to begin with, their lack of culturally appropriate repertoire and soft skills [and thus naturalizing] the hierarchy of people that leads to precarious immigrant access to the labour market. (Ku et al., 2018, p. 305)

Although these exclusionary effects of the CE requirements are well documented, little is known about *how* individuals understand and deal with CE as they seek employment in new labour markets.

In my doctoral research, I investigated learning processes of adults in migration-related transitions in Canada, examining how transitions can serve as an impetus for learning (Hof & Bernhard, 2022, 2023), how individuals engage with different forms of boundaries (Bernhard, 2022), how temporality is intertwined with transitions (Bernhard, 2023b), and how individuals from geographically diverse backgrounds find ways to deal with this particular challenge of CE and find ways to transition their prior work experience to new contexts (Bernhard, 2023a). In this paper I will build on the latter and will first outline the theoretical perspectives of doing transitions and doing migration that were drawn upon in this research. Second, I will briefly describe the methodological approach taken, before presenting and discussing the findings.

2 Theoretical Framework: Doing Migration and Transitions

To study learning during life course transitions, I adopt a doing transitions framework which asserts ...

that transitions do not simply exist but are constantly... shaped and produced through social practices, and that transitions emerge and are constantly reproduced and transformed through the interrelation of discourses, institutional regulation (including formal and informal pedagogical intervention), as well as individual processes of learning, education, and coping. (Walther et al., 2022, p. 5)

Through the interplay of these discursive, institutional, and individual modes of shaping transitions with material, temporal, and interpersonal relations, transitions are constantly produced and reproduced, also reproducing social differences in the process (Settersten et al., 2022, p. 240)

Migration as the movement across national boundaries can be explored as a particular form of doing transitions. Such a doing migration perspective views migration as the result of social practices that „turn mobile (and often also immobile) individuals into ‘migrants’” (Amelina, 2020, p. 2). Migration can then be understood as a relational process that constitutes migrants and within which individuals actively (re)position themselves regarding markers of differences. While constructing and shaping their transitions across boundaries, people put into relation their individual experiences, interpretations, and socially situated practices. This process of doing migration is associated with a variety of learning demands as both a barely escapable imposition and as an opportunity space, expressed in the ambivalence of migration *being done to* and *being done by* (Bernhard, 2022).

3 Research Design: Narrative Interviews and Documentary Method

I gathered data through biographical-narrative interviews (Chase, 2018; Schütze, 1983) in 2021 with 20 persons who had moved to Canada as adults. As this study is interested in post-arrival processes and in the (non)transfer of previously acquired skills and experiences, I selected participants based on their having moved to Canada three or more years ago and on having obtained postsecondary education outside of Canada before initial arrival. This focus on so-called ‘highly skilled migrants’ aims to bring into view the ambivalences of ostensible desirability – as expressed through skills-focused migration regimes – and the challenges faced by this group of migrants in successfully transitioning into the new labour market. Research participants were between 27 and 62 years of age and had arrived in Canada between 3 and 21 years prior. Interviews were conducted following the approach to narrative interviews as outlined by Schütze (1983), encouraging participants to „speak off the cuff about a part of their everyday life that is of interest to the researchers, be it their entire life story or just their working life” (Nohl, 2010, p. 196).

The data were analysed using the Documentary Method (DM) (Bohnsack, 2014; Nohl, 2010) which presupposes that „what is communicated verbally and explicitly in interview texts is not the only element of significance to the empirical analysis, but that it is above all necessary to reconstruct the meaning that underlies and is implied” (Nohl, 2010, p. 200). Put differently: the narrations document different patterns of experience, orientation, and action that are to be reconstructed. Thus, I interpreted not only *what* is being said but also reflected on *how* it is being said. Of interest were modes and figures of speech, such as positive or negative images, so-called *counter-horizons*, which point to participants’ implicit knowledge and frames of orientation. The goal was to reconstruct and contrast different forms of experiencing and processing work-life transitions in the context of migration.

4 Findings

In comparing different logics of practice in the data, I could identify three distinct modes of dealing with CE. The first mode, *replay and readjust*, is marked by repeated setbacks,

frustrations, and—seemingly—resignation. The second mode, *reset and move forward*, is marked by a lowering of aspirations and an alignment of future life course decisions with the need to acquire CE. The third mode, *research and pro-act*, is characterized by a focus on understanding how Canada functions to take advantage of that knowledge. Analysis of the 20 interviews indicated relevance of CE for 12 participants. Among those, the mode replay and readjust can be identified in two, reset and move forward in six, and research and pro-act in four interviews. Drawing on select interview passages, I will illuminate these modes of engaging with CE.

4.1 Replay and readjust

As a common experience, individuals must settle for „survival jobs”, often „hated” and well below the individuals’ levels of qualification. Yet, despite the often-repeated devaluation of experience and education, individuals learn the rules of the game and „press on,” even if returned to start several times.

Going beyond passively experiencing those setbacks, however, individuals actively engage with the situation, interpret the experience and act within their range of limited options. Such is the case for Jamila who had to settle for a job that she disliked, thereby gaining Canadian experience and references, which could then later attest to her experience. This acquisition of localized experience was particularly surprising for her as she gained work experience in the UK which she expected to be valued in Canada:

Coming back here it felt like the Canadians wanted you to have their Canadian something. Yes when you tell them they're like „oh okay yeah great you've worked in UK” ... I've done it in UK, some of them don't even understand what that means so what working in UK means it's like „why do you not understand that?” It's UK it's a- it's a developed country it's like Canada but they don't and so they don't appreciate it so that- that was like a shocker. (Jamila, lines 982-995)

Jamila's expectation of a seamless transition from the British to the Canadian labour market is not met. Instead, upon her return after working in the UK for several years „the Canadians wanted you to have their Canadian something“. The choice of the expression „something” can be interpreted as a perceived arbitrariness of the requirement for Canadian experience. Although her possession of a Canadian education was helpful in her transition from the UK to Canada, she found the non-recognition of professional experience to be „a shocker.“

To further improve her employment prospects beyond her current, disliked job, Jamila is pursuing volunteer work, for which she needs to receive some training. Referring to a situation in which she had to wait 45 minutes for a bus on a cold winter evening, Jamila is reflecting on the actions she must take:

It was really hard, this is a person who was driving now I have been reduced back to using a bus. these things I must do because I know volunteer- I can quote that as a Canadian experience and I'm struggling here finding a job because it's my UK experience Canadians are not really liking it for some reason so now I must start doing things that I'm gonna start you know adding on to my résumé. (Jamila, l. 724-729)

Jamila elaborates on her own theory of why she „must do” all those unpleasant things: the non-recognition of her professional experience in the UK. Although Jamila already had Canadian citizenship at that time, she uses „Canadians” as a group separate from herself. While Jamila takes action and moves forward, volunteer work appears to be less voluntary and rather a requirement „that has to be done” to acquire Canadian work experience.

In this form of engagement with CE, Jamila had to repeatedly adjust her horizons of possibilities and to recognize that her previous migration experience was of only limited value. Against this backdrop of challenges and recurring setbacks, she learns how to independently persist („press on”) as she shares repeatedly during the interview.

4.2 Reset and Move Forward

A second form of engaging with the CE demands can be described as *reset and move forward*. Here and in contrast to the previous form, aspirations are lowered, and future life course decisions aligned with the need to acquire CE. Although this does not preclude disappointment, the reduced expectations appear to open a way out of a repeated *replay and readjust*. Such was the case with Lishan, who – although no longer considering herself a new immigrant – feels in certain respects „shortchanged”. She had met the expectations placed on her, gained Canadian work experience, and obtained Canadian qualifications, yet she has not succeeded in finding employment commensurate with her skills.

Lishan talks about receiving a job offer unrelated to her professional training while she and her family were preparing to relocate within Canada to be closer to her husband’s workplace:

So over that weekend my husband and I talked about it, we talked about it, (.) this was an opportunity that I had found, we won’t guarantee that I’d find a job even if we move to Oakville straight away so we were going to take that job, we agreed: „let’s at least take this that has come and then maybe after you’ve gotten your Canadian experience the fam- (laughs) famous or infamous Canadian experience for a year or two then we can think of moving. (Lishan, l. 436-442)

In contrast to Jamila, who problematizes the exclusionary dimensions of CE, here the engagement with the „famous or infamous” CE affects big life course decisions to be made. Already having internalized the importance of possessing CE, Lishan and her husband agreed to postpone the family move in order to fulfil this requirement. Whereas Jamila was reduced to volunteering and working a job she hated, Lishan took a job unrelated to her field. CE appears as solely something to be acquired („gotten”) to be able to move on. The rather external interpretation of CE as something to possess reappears when Lishan shares her experience of repeated rejection in the labour market despite having Canadian education and some Canadian experience:

In a sense, there are times when- I’m no longer a new Canadian immigrant. I’d say Canada is home now for me, but there is still a sense in which you still feel shortchanged, is that you feel like you did everything that you’re supposed to have done, you have Canadian experience, for me it’s over seven years, I have a Canadian qualification now. (Lishan, l. 616-622)

Lishan begins the description of her situation with the relativizing expression „in a sense” and „there are times when” before she interrupts herself to insert that she is „no longer a new Canadian immigrant (...) Canada is home now for me”. This self-conception of being settled is, in a certain way, contrasted by Lishan feeling disadvantaged, unfairly treated, and „shortchanged”. She has adhered to the rules of the game, gained CE and qualifications, and yet cannot find suitable gainful employment. As a result, she cannot get away from an ascribed migrant identity and her arrival is not complete. This experience of disadvantage is generalized as being shared by others, which is documented by the repeated use of general „you”.

Here, the engagement with CE is marked by an acknowledgement of its importance and willingness to proactively align major life course decisions, such as the family move, with the need to acquire CE as a qualification. Yet, possessing CE appears to be necessary but not sufficient for her labour market success in light of other barriers. As a result, Lishan continues to

steadily move forward in search for the position she really wants despite having played by the rules of the game and acquired CE.

4.3 Research and Pro-act

A more pragmatic approach to dealing with CE can be termed *research and pro-act*, which is characterized by excelling at knowing the rules and playing the game. Here, the focus is less on adjusting expectations and more on understanding how Canada functions, in order to take advantage of that knowledge. For individuals transitioning to the new labour market in this mode, this means lots of research and networking as is the case with Dacian. Unlike Lishan, who also had a professional degree but gave up pursuing a career in her field, Dacian „of course” still has this as his goal, and „just wanted to use [his] time efficiently”. Contrasting with Jamila, who was repeatedly „shocked” and „surprised” by the way things worked, Dacian positions himself as „realistic” and approaches CE as a project to study, understand and engage with systematically:

Based on my experience with the different job search strategies, I decided to use online job search, and in-person job search, including cold calls, and just attending different employers on spot. And this is how I got my first job in Canada working in restaurants. Which gave me a really unique experience. Of course, was big difference from my work in Eastern Europe. I was building the foundation. (Dacian, l. 40-47)

Drawing on his existing biographical experience, Dacian strategically triangulates various job search strategies and seemingly without much trouble lands his first job in a restaurant. Not working in his field was not problematic for Dacian, as the job was a „unique experience” and provided the „foundation” for further steps. Like Lishan, Dacian appears to have accepted the importance of obtaining CE. Further, he takes courses towards his professional goal and enjoys researching the system, which he finds „very interesting”. Unlike Jamila, who repeatedly expressed surprise about the non-recognition of foreign experience, Dacian not only takes this as a given but has learned strategies to reduce the opacity of CE. He „researched the community”, learned that „networking is something very Canadian” and uses this knowledge to his advantage. There are, however, setbacks in Dacian’s quest to understand and navigate the Canadian system while he is working in a new position of a law clerk:

I received notice of termination of my employment, which was very good shock (...) obviously, they were not happy with me. But this lack of transparency that for almost two- two months, they didn’t share this with me. (...) So, I didn't know what was the problem, the accent, the lack of experience. So, they gave me very- very little explanations. (...). After my last workday, of course, I immediately resumed my networking. I don’t have time to lose. I refreshed my contacts, I started to look for another job. (Dacian, l. 112-127)

Being unexpectedly laid off from his position as a law clerk irritated Dacian’s mode of engaging with CE. Against the positive counter-horizon of being told what he did wrong and understanding „what can be changed”, the „lack of transparency” leaves him without a „real assessment” beyond the sense of the employer not being happy with him. Externalizing this challenge as an expression of the more closed nature of the Canadian culture, he „immediately” pivots to again strategically pursuing employment through networking.

In sum, this form of engagement with CE is marked by studying the system and learning the tools to deploy. Dacian recognizes that the non-recognition of foreign experience can have exclusionary effects and consequently approaches his job search methodically, including settling for a restaurant job to build a „foundation.” CE has meaning for him as an object to be studied and rules to be known in order to „know where you’re going”. As a result, Dacian

considers networking to be something particularly Canadian and embraces it as part of his job search strategy.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The three modes of engaging with the somewhat obscure but persistent requirement to obtain CE as a prerequisite for finding and sustaining adequate employment illuminate the diverse learning and development of working age adults, particularly in transitions. From a doing transitions perspective which highlights the *interrelation* of discourses, institutions and individual processes of learning, education and coping, the particular configuration of individual experience and discourse comes into focus. In the mode of *replay and readjust*, the CE discourse appears as a challenge that is to be faced repeatedly but cannot be surmounted. In the second mode of *reset and move forward*, CE appears as a force that significantly alters expectations, aspirations, and orientations. In the third mode, *research and pro-act*, CE acts as an impetus for learning about processes and researching the labour market, akin to a game to be understood and played.

In each of the modes, the engagement with CE is closely linked with learning and the acquisition of knowledge and competencies: First, it is the non-recognition of previously acquired knowledge and experience that makes obtaining CE necessary. Second, learning and shifting perspectives about oneself and the world can be the consequence of dealing with CE and be influenced by subjective theories of one's own learning (Säljö, 1979, 2021). Here, one can discern different forms of learning in the context of migratory transitions. As elaborated in more detail elsewhere (Bernhard, 2023b), dealing with the challenges of migration, including the requirement to obtain localized experience, can lead to transformative learning both in an expansive and restrictive sense but can also be accompanied by learning that is best described as tacit.

Beyond being solely an individual act however, this learning in transitions is socially embedded and mediated by social practices and relationships (Bernhard & Hof, 2023; Hof & Bernhard, 2022). First, relationally thinking of migration at an individual level brings into view the co-constitutive character of becoming a migrant: Individuals often experience incomplete and incongruent transitions, no longer self-identifying as newcomers, but being treated as such through the entanglement of self with others and with discourses. Against the backdrop of the CE discourse, the questioning and reconstruction of self-concepts come into view, providing both a requirement to reassess what biographical resources can be drawn upon, but also an opportunity space to redefine past experiences. Second, the engagement with the CE discourse is a shared experience as a heterogeneous group of individuals encounter and must deal with the same rulebook, however oblique and opaque it may be. While otherness is being (re-)produced through the CE discourse, outsiders may form a community of experience or of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991/2008), sharing a similar tacit knowledge of how to interpret and act on the demands placed upon them.

In addition to these implications for theorizing learning in transitions, the findings of this study also provide insights into how best working age adults' learning and development can be guided against the backdrop of individuals' diverse experiences. The insights into the three different modes of engaging with the CE discourse can be used to identify, trial and validate the range of educative experiences in educational, workplace and community settings that support worklife transitions in the context of migration. These supports may refer to sustaining individuals' current employment, advancing further their capacities in that field or advancing a different and new occupational or career trajectory. This means that a better understanding of the different expressions of agency identified in migration „being done by” might serve as impetus for supporting the development of resilience in the mode „replay and readjust”, for guiding the active reassessment of opportunities, acceptance, and alignment of life course decisions

in the mode „reset and move forward”, and for providing information about intricate aspects of the labour market in the mode „research and proact.” Although the research was conducted in Canada, the implications appear relevant also in other contexts as public support for selective professional immigration policies increases and the ambivalence between ostensible desirability of ‘skilled migrants’ and complex barriers to employment persist. Recognizing distinct modes of engaging with and learning from challenges may serve as an impetus to differentiate support and guidance to individuals from diverse backgrounds as they navigate worklife transitions in an increasingly mobile and diverse world.

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Biographical notes

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